

STRUCTURAL HIERARCHY OF FIBROUS COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Scale levels and characteristic dimensions of structural elements have been distinguished in the problems of micromechanics, macromechanics and mechanics of structures. It was shown in numerous examples that structural hierarchy is essential in selecting the analytical design methods and tests, in the problems of technological mechanics.

1. THE SCOPE OF CONSIDERATION

In traditional continuum mechanics we generally distract ourselves from the material structure. The analysis is performed on the scale of the characteristic dimension of a structural element: length, width, and thickness. The ratios of these dimensions which form the geometric shape of a bar, plate, and shell are laid into the basis of the determining kinematic hypotheses (thick, thin, long, short). Fibrous composites are multiple-scale materials with structural hierarchy [1]. In other words, composite materials or structures are composed of recurring elements of structure which, in their turn, have their own structure. Therefore several levels of consideration are possible.

In the problems of engineering mechanics the structure of fibrous composites has been considered within a wide range on the dimensional scale. Three levels of consideration - micro-, macromechanics, and structural mechanics - are distinguished on the dimensional scale. The problem is that each structural level has to be considered as a continuum. There appear specific problems in passing over to continuum in each range. The continuity of the object of study in passing over one scale to another must be emphasized.

Micromechanics operates with the inter-fiber distance within a lamina; a fiber diameter is the scale of consideration (Table 1). Though in stress-strain calculation in the zone with stress concentrators we have to deal with a scale more times less than the fiber thickness so that the stress singularity near the fibers on the scale of reinforcing elements could be taken into account. The passing over to a unidirectional lamina is the result of averaging. Rotation of fibers round the material axes within the plane of orientation allows one to characterize the properties of a monolayer in case of loading at an angle to the reinforcement direction.

In macromechanics the thickness of a unidirectional lamina is the scale (Table 2). For multilayered

MICROMECHANICS

Table 1.

Object	Scale	Applications	Test Methods
<p data-bbox="418 350 502 372">Lamina</p> <p data-bbox="367 972 560 994">Ply homogenization</p>	<p data-bbox="703 440 874 462">Fiber diameter d_f</p> <p data-bbox="731 613 840 636">Variables:</p> <p data-bbox="686 669 884 692">Interfiber distance a</p> <p data-bbox="686 725 884 748">Angle of rotation θ°</p>	<p data-bbox="947 440 1158 490">Structural mechanics of laminated media</p> <p data-bbox="925 552 1175 574">Structural strength theory</p> <p data-bbox="947 641 1152 664">Stress concentrations</p>	<p data-bbox="1204 440 1421 608">Investigation of mechanical and physical properties of components by physical and mechanical methods</p> <p data-bbox="1238 669 1380 748">Estimation of component interaction</p>

MACROMECHANICS

Table 2.

Object	Scale	Applications	Test Methods
<p data-bbox="367 364 555 386">Homogeneous Ply</p>	<p data-bbox="708 364 879 414">Thickness of i-th lamina h_i</p> <p data-bbox="708 476 879 526">Thickness of layer package H</p> $H = \sum_{i=1}^n h_i$ <p data-bbox="742 683 845 705"><u>Variables:</u></p> <p data-bbox="708 739 879 795">$h_i, \theta_i, \theta(y), h(y)$, Layup</p>	<p data-bbox="965 364 1135 414">Averaging of ply properties</p> <p data-bbox="965 476 1152 526">Characterization of off-axis properties</p> <p data-bbox="965 588 1152 638">Summation through layer thickness</p> <p data-bbox="947 705 1169 784">Passage to the limit to structurally-anisotropic medium</p>	<p data-bbox="1204 448 1426 638">Investigation of mechanical properties of lamina by destructive methods and physical properties by non-destructive methods</p>

media, the object of consideration is a laminated plate, thickness of which is determined by the number and thicknesses of laminae. The theory of laminated plates is based on the concept of a monolayer, and it allows us to consider the stacking sequence of laminae, and the law of through-the-thickness fiber orientation $\theta(h)$.

As a rule, the sizes of structural elements exceed several times the plate thickness. In the structural mechanics the characteristic sizes of the articles are the scale, while the object of investigation is the structural element with averaged strain characteristics (Table 3). Thereby the geometric parameters of structural elements must also be considered, along with the law of reinforced laminae layup. This gives a possibility to select and evaluate the areas of applicability of the traditional hypotheses used in the development of the design methods for structurally-anisotropic materials. The number of structural elements through the thickness of package on each level of consideration should be sufficiently to enable us to make the transition from discrete medium to a continuum can be performed, without a great error. The netted shells make up a special class of composite structures. Their analogue in nature is cellular structures with one phase rigid and another one either empty space or liquid. A specific feature of extremely light netted structures (with or without coating) is the presence of an elementary cell. It acts as a recurring element of structure. Transition to a continuum is performed by translation of a cell in two directions (along the axial and circumferential coordinates). The necessary condition of the transition is expressed as $L_1/L \ll 1$, where L_1 is the maximal characteristic size of a cell, L is the minimal dimension of the structure (Table 4). The specifics in construction the continual model involves the taking into account the deformation of ribs in bending in the plane of rib placement when determining the generalised stiffnesses from the parameters of the structure. Then from the obtained deformations of the entire package the forces in ribs are calculated [2]

2. PROCESSING PROBLEMS

The structural hierarchy of fibrous composites determines the specifics of fabrication process of composite parts and structures. It must be kept in mind that, strictly speaking, composites are not the materials in the traditional sense, i.e. they are not finished items with fixed predetermined properties. Composites are being created from semi-fabricated articles simultaneously with structure. It is interesting to note that moulding process of composite articles can also be divided into three large blocks: fiber \rightarrow lamina \rightarrow laminated medium; the scale of consideration is preserved. The impregnated filaments form a monolayer or reinforcing framework (with subsequent impregnation). This is the way of producing a semi-fabricated article. After the multilayered or spatially reinforced medium is made from semi-fabricated articles by different processes - contact moulding, pressing, winding, and braiding. The scale of consideration and, primarily, the thickness of the article to be made plays a great role in the problems of technological mechanics of composites and in selecting the processes. Due to extremely low heat conductivity, there is the danger of binder squeezing out and fiber curvature, and, therefore, fabrication of thick-walled articles has so far been problematic [3]. It is assumed in constructing Tables 1...4 that the reinforcement was rectilinear and regularly packed within the recurring element of structure. In reality the deviations from the idealized scheme - fiber curvature and disordering packing, and initial imperfections, are observed. These deviations can be random and specified ones. In the latter case it is possible to develop materials which stiffen in the deformation process at the expense of complete or partial (as in the reinforcing elements - ropes or veins) fiber straightening. It is necessary to emphasize the role of sizes of the structural elements and their packing in the vicinity of imperfections and holes. In fibrous composites the fiber sizes and their packing determine fracture viscosity and localization of microdamages. Therefore, it is

STRUCTURAL MECHANICS (CONTINUOUS STRUCTURES)

Table 3.

Object	Scale	Applications	Test Methods
<p data-bbox="377 404 587 426">Structural Elements</p>	<p data-bbox="707 404 925 454">Geometric parameters of articles H, R, L</p> <p data-bbox="701 518 930 658">Parameters of accuracy estimation of the Saint-Venant's, Kirchhoff-Love's, Timoshenko's hypotheses $H/L, H/R$</p> <p data-bbox="710 689 922 740">Physical relationships E_i / G_{ij}</p>	<p data-bbox="949 404 1202 510">Calculation methods with allowance of turn and compressibility of normals</p> <p data-bbox="963 574 1188 624">Interlaminar shear and transverse tension</p> <p data-bbox="966 689 1202 740">Edge and end effects of singularities</p>	<p data-bbox="1236 432 1438 538">Estimation of load-carrying capacity by direct and indirect methods.</p> <p data-bbox="1231 574 1448 624">Testing of specimens-witnesses</p>

STRUCTURAL MECHANICS (NETTED AND CELLULAR STRUCTURES)

Table 4

Object	Scale	Applications	Test Methods
<p data-bbox="382 426 594 449">Structural Elements</p>	<p data-bbox="748 428 894 451">L_1 is a cell size.</p> <p data-bbox="701 488 941 510">Condition of realization:</p> <p data-bbox="773 574 865 596">$L_1/L \ll 1$</p> <p data-bbox="701 630 935 764">Introduction of the linear dimensions of the ribs into the formulae for calculation of characteristics</p>	<p data-bbox="966 432 1192 482">Method of calculations taking into account</p> <p data-bbox="970 518 1202 572">→ forces in the cells of cells;</p> <p data-bbox="963 608 1197 686">→ bending of plane and curvilinear ribs in the layup plane</p> <p data-bbox="983 745 1188 880">Micropolar theory of elasticity and its application to the description of netted structures</p>	<p data-bbox="1236 462 1448 596">.Determination of the settlement of compressed shells for evaluation of the elastic characteristics</p> <p data-bbox="1257 664 1427 686">Buckling analysis</p>

expedient that high density of structural elements near the areas of disturbed stress state (holes, imperfections, edges) be attained. Thus the problems connected with the error in transition to continuum in these areas arise. The isolation of local zones where the consideration is to be done on another structural level is a widely used technique. The so-called locally-global approach used in the analysis of edge effect [4] can serve as an example.

3. TWO APPROACHES

Within the framework of hierarchical approach on each structural level, different directions of the mechanics of composites are formed which allow one to successively consider the properties of components, reinforcement layout in the lamina and packing over the thickness of the package in solving concrete problems. In developing the design methods and tests two principally different approaches are adopted. In the *structural approach* the analysis is performed on the level of the recurring element with subsequent transition to continuum. The thing is that the largest structural elements in scale (fibers or large heterogeneous inclusions) determine fracture toughness and localization of microdamages. On the structural level of the reinforcing elements the problems of strength, fracture mechanics, singularity of stress distributions (stress concentrations) are considered. For a three-dimensional analysis with necessary detailization, i.e. examining the details in compliance with local inhomogeneity and nonlinearity, imperfections and cracks etc., the finite element technique is the basic calculation method.

In the *quasi-uniform approach* the continuum mechanics is employed involving the introduction of averaged material characteristics. Their determination is the object of the theory of reinforced media. The main area of application the problems of stiffness, buckling vibrations of bars, plates, and shells. A complete application requires that a detailed analysis of kinematic and geometric hypotheses be performed. The determining scientific results have been obtained in this field, and vast engineering experience accumulated. The results analysis is presented in [5].

4. AREAS OF APPLICATION

A typical example of the hierarchical approach is the analytical evaluation of load-carrying capacity of multidimensional composites. In strength problems it is necessary to take a recourse to the structural level of the reinforcing elements (a reverse problem). The approach when multidimensional medium is represented as a set of monotropic rod-type unidirectional elements - rectilinear or curvilinear ones [6]. The spatial arrangement of elements simulates the structure of the reinforcement. The procedure of solving consists in finding out the relation between the tensor of averaged stresses of composite in the principal axes of elastic symmetry and the tensor of structural stresses in the system of principal axes of monotropy of the structural element. This allows one to introduce the characteristics of the reinforcement and matrix into the calculation and - in terms of the parameter of material orientation - the placement of the reinforcement. Further the ultimate stresses in the composites σ^{ult} are calculated from the ultimate stresses in the structural elements according to the specified strain tensor. Stress σ^{ult} is evaluated for a specified stress state from the selected strength criterion for a structural element. The choice of the strength criterion for spatially reinforced composites is a complex independent task. In many respects, it is connected with the peculiarities of fracture mechanics, in particular, with localization of the fracture process over several spatial cells.

The hierarchical approach can also be traced in the problems of fracture mechanics. On the level of the reinforcing elements there are always present microdefects in fibrous composites. The initiation and propagation of damages are observed on all scale levels. The scale of the initial imperfection changes - breakage of elementary fibers, intra-lamina fracture, breakage of elementary lamina, interlaminar delamination and peeling, first-ply failure, and gradual fracture of the package as a whole. The central moment is the change from the initial imperfection into a through-crack. The development of models for a wide range on the dimensional scale is the task of the future. The methods, objectives and tasks of testing are selected on each scale level. On the level of the reinforcing elements, the properties of the reinforcing fibers and matrix, and their interaction are studied. The properties of components are measured by the traditional methods, whereas the study of the interaction in the system *fiber-matrix* needs special methods. Characterization of the composites is performed on the level of a monolayer by mechanical and physical methods. This is the central question because the testing of anisotropic materials is a comparatively novel and scarcely studied field of mechanics [7]. Finally, in structural mechanics the tests are aimed at studying the load-carrying capacity of the article or its elements in general, mainly by non-destructive methods and determination of the material properties of the structure on specimens-witnesses.

The different compartments of the mechanics of composites which interrelate the different areas of investigations and aspects of the problem under consideration, have not been evolved to the same extent [8, 9]. For their further development and success, the understanding of the hierarchical nature of composites is of essential significance.

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